

EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING GEOGRAPHY IN ACADEMIC LYCEUMS AND VOCATIONAL SCHOOLS USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

Shodiyev Kh.R.

Associate Professor on Geography and Economic Fundamentals, Navoi State Pedagogical
Institute, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14030900>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the issues related to teaching geography in academic lyceums and vocational schools using information technology tools and distance learning systems. It reviews the work of scholars on these challenges and presents proposals and recommendations for addressing them. Additionally, it offers a structure for integrating information educational environments and teaching methods in geography lessons. The effectiveness of this proposed structure has been validated through experimental studies using the Student-Fisher criterion to determine its effectiveness.*

Keywords: *information educational environment, Teaching Method, Educational Tool, Creative Thinking, Competence, Student-Fisher.*

Introduction:

Currently, there is a growing need to utilize information educational environments to effectively organize the educational process in academic lyceums and vocational schools and to enhance the efficiency of teaching subjects, including geography [1]. Information educational environments play a crucial role in providing knowledge along with additional information, particularly in visualizing geographic processes and phenomena.

The content of geography education in academic lyceums and vocational schools includes optimizing the use of natural resources, evaluating wealth for the development of economic sectors, and developing forecasts for environmental changes that may arise as a result of resource extraction and production [2-7]. Topics related to studying the significance of managing natural-anthropogenic processes and the overall integral geosystem are also included.

To effectively convey these topics to students, utilizing didactic educational tools integrated into information educational environments—such as interactive maps, multimedia applications, presentations, virtual teaching technologies, video lessons, online open and closed tests, and crosswords—serves as important pedagogical tools. These resources enhance students' motivation towards the subject, help them understand specific geographic issues, facilitate knowledge assimilation from textbooks, shape their perceptions, and direct them towards independent learning [8-10].

Using multimedia applications and interactive educational tools offers several advantages over traditional printed visual aids. With conventional aids, students can view an entire structure of an event or process simultaneously, which can complicate the understanding of geography's essence. In contrast, multimedia and interactive visual aids allow students to revisit specific parts or phenomena multiple times to grasp the details more thoroughly [11].

Therefore, there is a necessity to develop a cohesive mechanism for using information educational environments in geography lessons.

Literature Review: Research into the theory and practice of teaching geography in academic lyceums and vocational schools has explored various aspects, including the forms, methods, and tools of geography education, the challenges of employing information technology and distance learning systems, the development of students' creativity through computer technologies, and methodologies for forming students' competencies. These studies have been conducted by researchers both in our country and abroad, including A.B. Janzakov, P. Ghulomov, R. Qurbonniyozov, A. Soatov, and others [12-15].

In the referenced studies, while there have been some proposals regarding the theory and practice of using information technology tools and distance learning systems in teaching geography in academic lyceums and vocational schools, a comprehensive system for utilizing information educational environments specifically in geography education has not been thoroughly investigated. Therefore, the proposed research aimed at improving the methodology for using information educational environments in teaching geography in these institutions is considered a pressing issue.

Research Methodology. Currently, specific mechanisms have been developed for employing information technology tools in geography lessons within academic lyceums and vocational schools. However, there is a growing need to further enhance these mechanisms by incorporating search systems from global networks, educational platforms, and information educational environments into geography education [12,15]. The proposed research aims to enhance the effectiveness of teaching geography by utilizing information educational environments. Furthermore, there is an emerging need to employ unconventional teaching methods to spark student interest. One effective approach is to use integrated lessons that combine geography with subjects like computer science and information technology. This method allows for geography lessons to be conducted in a vibrant and comprehensive manner, ensuring the interconnectedness of subjects, practical application of theoretical knowledge, and development of skills in using computer technologies. Such lessons also stimulate cognitive activities among students and encourage independent learning [14]. Consequently, these lessons enhance each student's motivation and creative potential, leading to an increase in their cognitive interest [15 16]. Thus, we have developed a lesson structure and stages that integrate information educational environments, didactic learning tools, and teaching methods into the geography curriculum of academic lyceums and vocational schools (look at image 1).

The recommended structure for organizing geography lessons in academic lyceums and vocational schools aims to enhance students' motivation for the subject, develop creative thinking, and shape their competencies regarding the causes of existing problems in nature and ways to address them. This proposed structure is based on the methodology of integrating information educational environments and the didactic electronic educational resources placed within them with teaching methods.

In this context, based on the characteristics of geography topics, methods such as debate, brainstorming, scavenger hunts, pinboards, journals, general brainstorming, video puzzles, synquains, blitz surveys, and clustering are recommended for use, along with the assessment method for evaluating students' knowledge. These teaching methods are considered effective in organizing geography lessons in academic lyceums and vocational schools.

1st Image. Structure of Organizing Geography Lessons in Academic Lyceums and Vocational Schools.

Analysis and Results.

In order to enhance the effectiveness of teaching geography in academic lyceums and vocational schools and to organize students' extracurricular activities effectively, experimental studies were conducted within the framework of the research to determine the effectiveness level

of using the proposed structure, including information educational environments. The experimental studies were carried out in academic lyceums and vocational schools in the Navoi region. Students in these academic lyceums and vocational schools involved in the experimental studies were divided into experimental and control groups. It was recommended that the experimental groups utilize the proposed structure developed within the research framework.

The control classes and groups were not given this opportunity. The results of the students involved in this experimental study were analyzed, and in order to verify their reliability, mathematical-statistical analysis was conducted based on the Student-Fisher criterion. In using this criterion, the

$A \% = \frac{\bar{x}}{3} \cdot 100\% - \frac{\bar{y}}{3} \cdot 100\%$ formula was applied to determine the corresponding average values

$\bar{X} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^4 n_i X_i$ and the dispersion coefficients $D_n = \sum_{i=1}^4 \frac{n_i (x_i - \bar{X})^2}{n-1}$ for the samples. According

to the calculation results, the average assimilation rate of the experimental class and group was found to be higher than that of the control class and group, showing an increase of 10.6%.

Conclusion.

The integration of information educational environments with methods such as debate, brainstorming, scavenger hunts, pinboards, journals, general brainstorming, video puzzles, synquains, blitz surveys, clustering, and assessment methods in lesson activities has proven effective in enhancing the efficiency of teaching geography in academic lyceums and vocational schools, as established during the research. Therefore, it is necessary to widely implement the proposed hypothesis in the educational and upbringing processes of academic lyceums and vocational schools.

By utilizing the recommended methodology, it is possible to enhance students' interest in geography through the presentation of predictions regarding changes in the environment that may arise from the placement and development of productive forces, as well as natural-anthropogenic processes that may occur within the natural environment, economic, and population systems, and to present the overall integrated geosystem dynamics in a visual manner. This approach will help develop students' creative thinking, scientific literacy, and practical competencies in geography.

REFERENCES

1. Janzakov A.B. Improving the mechanisms of teaching geography in general education schools through information technologies // PhD dissertation in Pedagogical Sciences. – Samarkand, 2021. – 143 p.
2. G'ulomov P., Qurboniyozov R. Natural Geography // Textbook for the 5th grade of general secondary education schools, 3rd edition. – Tashkent, 2011. – 96 p.
3. Soatov A., Abdulqosimov A., Mirakmalov M. Natural Geography // Textbook for 6th grade students of general secondary education schools. – Tashkent, 2017. – 160 p.
4. G'ulomov P., Vahobov H., Baratov P., Mamatqulov M. Geography (Natural Geography of Central Asia, Natural Geography of Uzbekistan) // Textbook for 7th grade students of general secondary education schools, 5th edition. – Tashkent, 2017. – 176 p.
5. Musayev P., Musayev J. Geography (Economic and Social Geography of Uzbekistan) // Textbook for 8th grade students of general secondary education schools, 6th edition. – Tashkent, 2017. – 176 p.

6. Qayumov A., Safarov I., Tillaboyeva M., Fedorko V. Geography (World Economic and Social Geography) // Textbook for 9th grade students of general secondary education schools, 6th edition. – Tashkent, 2017. – 177 p.
7. Sharipov Sh.M., Fedorko V.N., Safarova N.I., Rafiqov V.A. Geography (Practical Geography) // Textbook for 10th grade students of general secondary educational institutions and for students of secondary special and vocational education institutions, 1st edition. – Tashkent, 2017. – 160 p.
8. Mitrofanova Y.V. Features of organizing students' educational activities when working with an electronic textbook in the 7th grade // Geography and Ecology in the 21st Century School. – Moscow, 2004. – No. 2. – pp. 56-63.
9. Sheinis A.I. Methodology for using the Internet in distance learning on global problems of humanity in the 10th grade geography course // Abstract of the dissertation for the candidate of pedagogical sciences. – St. Petersburg, 2000. – 18 p.
10. Zabolotnova E.Yu. Methodological approaches to using geographic information educational resources and developing author's educational applications: based on the example of training students and improving the skills of geography teachers // Abstract of the dissertation for the candidate of pedagogical sciences. – Moscow, 2008. – 18 p.
11. Podvalnaya E.V. Multimedia presentations as a means of enhancing the effectiveness of the geography teaching process in special (correctional) schools of the 8th type // Abstract of the dissertation for the candidate of pedagogical sciences. – Moscow, 2010. – 18 p.
12. Kalinovskaya M.A. Using electronic educational resources in geography lessons as a condition for achieving education quality // School Pedagogy. – 2015. – No. 2. – pp. 25-27.
13. Mitrofanova Y.V. Formation of individual experience in creative activities of students using new pedagogical technologies while studying geography of their locality // Abstract of the dissertation for the candidate of pedagogical sciences. – St. Petersburg, 2005. – 18 p.
14. Musataeva I.S. Methodology for developing and using information and communication technology tools for shaping geometric competence in middle school students // Dissertation for the candidate of pedagogical sciences. – Almaty, 2008. – 227 p.
15. Naderi M.G. Psychological and pedagogical foundations of using information and communication technologies as a means of enhancing the effectiveness of the teaching process in geography lessons in schools of the Islamic Republic of Iran // Abstract of the dissertation for the candidate of pedagogical sciences. – Dushanbe, 2012. – 18 p.
16. Scheyvens, R., Griffin, A.L., Jocoy, C.L., Liu, Y., and Bradford, M. 2008. Experimenting with active learning in Geography: dispelling the myths that perpetuate resistance. *Journal of Geography in Higher Education* 32(1): 51-69.